

FAILURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE SINGLE LAP BONDED JOINTS

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SUMMARY: A methodology is presented for the failure prediction of composite single-lap bonded joints considering both of composite adherend failure and bondline failure. An elastic-perfectly plastic model of adhesive and a delamination failure criterion are used in the methodology. The failure predictions have been performed using finite element method and the proposed methodology. The failure prediction results such as failure mode and strength have very good agreements with the test results of the joint specimens with various bonding methods and parameters. The influence of variations in the effective strength (that is, adhesion performance) and plastic behavior of adhesive on the failure characteristics of the composite bonded joints are investigated numerically. The numerical results show that optimal joint strength is archived when adhesive and delamination failure occur at the same time.

KEYWORDS: Composite bonded joints, failure prediction, adhesive failure, single lap.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are generally two kinds of joining methods for composite structures: (1) mechanical fastening and (2) adhesive bonding. For the mechanical fastening, a number of holes should be machined in composite parts and these may cause problems in stress concentration and weight increase of the structures. The adhesively bonded joint is more efficient than mechanical fastening because the load transfer between composite parts is more uniformly performed through larger area.

Composite bonded joints have many parameters that influence their failure mode and strength. At first, two kinds of bonding methods can be considered: co-curing and secondary bonding. Co-curing is usually preferred over secondary bonding because the number of parts is reduced by using co-curing and the structural performance and reliability of co-curing method is expected to be better than those of secondary bonding. But co-cured assembly of large and complex composite structure requires large fabrication facility and complex tooling. In this case, the secondary bonding is a useful process to replace the co-curing method.

The co-cured joint can either be manufactured with or without adhesive. In the co-cured joints with adhesive (usually, adhesive film), the adhesive is cured at the same cure condition as CFRP prepreg. Therefore, there are few parameters in the co-curing method as compared to the secondary bonding method which have many parameters such as various surface conditions, bondline thickness, fillets, etc.

There are many choices of bonding methods and parameters in designing the composite bonded joints. For practical applications of the useful composite bonded joints, it is very important to know failure mechanism and behaviors according to bonding methods and other bonding parameters. The understanding of failure mechanism and behaviors is also essential for accurate and reliable failure prediction. Thus, many researchers investigated the influences

of various parameters on the failure behaviors in previous studies on composite bonded joints [1-8]. In these studies, the bonding parameters included surface conditions (e.g. contamination, abrasion, and plasma treatment), fillet, bondline thickness, surface ply angle, stacking sequence, environmental conditions, etc.

Many researchers also performed failure prediction of the composite bonded joints [5-9]. There are usually two kinds of failure prediction methods in the previous studies: one is stress or strain based method and the other is fracture mechanics approach. The stress or strain based method utilized failure criterion equations which include maximum stresses or strains in the bonded joint. This method is simple but may be not suitable because there are stress or strain singularities in the bonded joints. In the fracture mechanics method, initial crack is assumed and crack growth is assessed by comparing computed strain energy release rate with fracture toughness determined by experiments. The fracture toughness is different according to mode mix ratio as well as failure modes (for example, interfacial, cohesive, and delamination failure). So, the fracture toughness test is time (and cost) consuming process. In addition, the fracture mechanics method is not suitable for the bonded joint which fails without initial crack.

Although these two methods have merits and demerits as above mentioned, there is a common weak point in the previous studies which used these methods. The weak point is that most studies considered only one failure mode which was observed in previous experiments. However, various failure modes may appear according to mechanical properties of adhesive or bonding methods in the composite bonded joints. For example, the test results of Ref. [1] showed that progressive interfacial failure occurred in secondary bonded single lap joint but catastrophic delamination failure occurred in co-cured specimens with adhesive film. In this case, failure loads of the specimens were also changed according to change of failure modes although these specimens have the same geometry. Therefore, if the failure mode is changed due to the bonding methods or adhesive used, above two methods predict wrong failure loads. Most previous studies also have another demerit. This is that plastic behavior of adhesive material was not considered. In the bonded joint, local part of adhesive layer becomes early plastic region due to highly stress concentration before the final failure. This plastic behavior also changes stress and strain distributions in the adhesive layer as well as adherend part near to stress concentration region.

This paper presents a failure prediction method which considers plastic behaviour of adhesive and various failure modes which can occur in composite single lap bonded joints. The failure prediction results are compared with previous test results [1]. The effects of adhesion strength and plastic behaviour of adhesive layer were also investigated.

2. FAILURE PREDICTION METHOD

According to the previous studies [1], there are two major kinds of failure modes in composite single lap bonded joints. One is failure of adhesive layer which includes interfacial failure and cohesive failure of adhesive. This type of failure may be called bondline failure in overall concept. The other is delamination failure of composite adherends. The characteristic of the first was progressive failures which accompany plastic deformation and crack propagation of the adhesive layer. The characteristic of the second was catastrophic failure which occurred abruptly due to delamination failure without initial crack.

The present failure prediction method utilizes two kinds of failure criteria which consider separately bondline and delamination failure. Therefore, critical failure mode and failure load can be simultaneously determined by the present method. The details of the present method are described in the following.

2.1 Adhesive Failure Criterion Using Elastic-Perfectly Plastic Model

Elastic-perfectly plastic model as shown in Fig. 1 was used to predict the progressive failure of the adhesive layer. This is a simple failure model for the progressive failure analysis.

Fig. 1 : Elastic-perfectly plastic material model for adhesive.

For this failure model, plastic region is initiated at corner of overlap region in which stress concentration occurs. The plastic region propagates along the adhesive layer as applied load increases. When overall region of the adhesive layer becomes plastic region, final failure occurs without supporting any more load increase. This failure concept has been already used in Ref. [9] and physically consistent with the characteristics of the progressive failure of the adhesive layer. However, a difference between the present method and the previous one [9] is that bulk adhesive strength are used in Ref. [9] but not in the present method. Instead, the present method uses “effective ultimate stress” of the thin adhesive layer. The effective ultimate stress is obtained from correlation between experimental and numerical failure loads of reference single lap specimens. This adjusted strength value in the thin adhesive layer is called as the “effective ultimate stress” herein.

This “effective ultimate stress” concept is reasonable with three reasons. First, the ultimate stress of the thin adhesive layer may be different to that of bulk material due to interaction between adhesive and adherends. Second, some range of the joint strength variations due to surface conditions of the adherends can be considered by the “effective ultimate stress” if not unsuitable surface conditions. Third reason is that present method can consider plastic behaviour of the adhesive layer. The consideration of the plastic behaviour helps accurate stress calculations in adherend near the stress concentration region and also accurate failure prediction of delamination failure of adherend by using this stress results.

2.2 Delamination Failure Criterion of Composite Adherends

Onset of delamination failure usually means final failure in the composite single lap joints [1]. The present study uses a quadratic delamination criterion [10] as the following to predict the delamination failure of the composite adherends.

$$\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{yy}^2}{Y_T} + \frac{\sigma_{xy}^2}{S_{xy}}} = 1 \quad (1)$$

where σ_{xy} , σ_{yy} are interlaminar stresses, Y_T and S_{XY} are transverse tensile strength and in-plane shear strength of the composite material. This method is stress-based assessment. The stress-based assessments usually require determinations of two kinds of parameters, that is,

characteristic (or critical) distance and stress allowables. Y_T and S_{XY} correspond to the stress allowables which are obtain from coupon test of composite materials. The characteristic distance is needed because stress or strain singularity exists in the single lap bonded joints. In the present study, the characteristic distance was determined by using test results of the reference specimens in which delamination failures occurred in previous study [1].

3. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Numerical analyses of the composite single lap bonded joints were carried out using finite element models and the proposed failure prediction method. The single lap bonded joints referred to the previous experimental study in Ref. [1]. The details of bonding process and test results of the joint specimens are also described in Ref. [1]. Geometry and finite element model are shown in Fig. 2. The finite element model in Fig. 2 corresponds to the joint specimen with adhesive layer.

Fig. 2 : Geometry and FE-model of composite single lap joint with adhesive

Composite adherend is a uni-directional lay-up $[0]_{10T}$. Mechanical properties of the composite material (HT145/RS1222, Hankuk Fiber Glass Inc., Korea) are as follows.

$E_{11}=119\text{GPa}$	$E_{22}=9.28\text{GPa}$	$G_{12}=4.64\text{GPa}$
$\nu_{12}=0.34$	$Y_T=34.1\text{GPa}$	$S_{XY}=88.9\text{GPa}$

Other mechanical properties of the composite were obtained from $E_{33}=E_{22}$, $G_{13}=G_{12}$, $\nu_{13}=\nu_{12}$, $\nu_{23}=0.59$, $G_{23}=E_{22}/2(1+\nu_{23})=2.93\text{GPa}$. Types of adhesives used in the specimens and their mechanical properties are as follows.

- EA9309NA adhesive : $E=2.45\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.30$
- EA9309.3NA adhesive : $E=2.62\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.38$
- FM73 adhesive : $E=2.87\text{GPa}$, $\nu=0.40$

Nonlinear finite element analyses were performed using commercial software, MSC/MARC. 8-node plane strain elements were used in the FE-model. Boundary and loading condition of the FE-model are shown in Fig. 2. The comparisons of failure predictions and the previous experimental results were made for five kinds of joint specimens as shown in Table 1. Each of composite and adhesive material was assumed to be elastic and elastic-perfectly plastic.

Table 1 : Types of joint specimens for comparison between failure prediction and test results.

No.	Bonding method	Adhesive	Fillet	Test failure mode [1]
1	Secondary bonding	EA9309.3NA	None	Bondline failure
2	Secondary bonding	EA9309NA	None	Bondline failure
3	Secondary bonding	EA9309NA	Fillet	Bondline failure
4	Co-curing	FM73	None	100% delamination
5	Co-curing	None	None	100% delamination

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Determination of Failure Criterion Parameters

Failure criterion parameters such as the effective ultimate stresses of the adhesives and the characteristic distance should be determined first for the failure prediction. The effective ultimate stress for each adhesive was determined by using test results of reference joint specimens which failed in bondline failure mode. Results of the effective ultimate stress are shown in Table 2. Effective ultimate stresses of EA9309NA and EA9309.3NA were determined from test specimen no.1 and no.3 of Table 1. Because the specimens with FM73 failed by delamination, the effective ultimate stress of FM73 adhesive was determined from test data of bonded joint in metal adherends (refer to manufacturer's data in Ref. [11]).

Table 2 : Effective ultimate stress results of adhesives.

Adhesive	Bulk adhesive ultimate stress (MPa)	Effective adhesive ultimate stress (MPa)	Reference specimen
EA9309.3NA	36.3	46.8	Specimen no.1
EA9309NA	34.5	45.5	Specimen no.3
FM73	60.4	77.4	Bonded joint in metal [11]

The calculated values of the effective ultimate stresses were about 30 percents higher than the bulk adhesive ultimate stresses. Therefore, the effective strengths of the thin adhesive layers in the bonded joints are seemed to be based on the bulk adhesive materials and also consider interactions between adhesive and adherends.

The characteristic distance was determined using two specimens, that is, co-cured specimens with and without FM73 adhesive which failed in delamination failure mode. For this purpose, interfacial stresses in the specimens were calculated under test value of the failure load. The characteristic distance was determined as a location in which the delamination failure criterion equation was satisfied. The characteristic distance is identical as a value of 0.432mm in both reference specimens.

4.2 Comparison of Failure Prediction and Experimental Results

Failure predictions and test results of the secondary bonding specimen with EA9309.3NA adhesives are compared in Fig. 3. Fig. 3(a) shows load-displacement curve and Fig. 3(b) indicates load vs. delamination failure index curve. Failure index 1 means the joint failure due to the delamination. Both test and analysis results in Fig. 3(a) show that displacement increases as the load increases until it reaches a certain point then only displacement increases without load increase. This phenomenon indicates the bondline failure in which the entire adhesive layers turn into complete plastic region. According to the delamination failure index result, the delamination failure of composite materials does not occur until the joint specimen reaches the bondline failure. Therefore, major failure mode of the secondary bonded specimen is the bondline failure and the failure load is about 13.8kN. This result is in very good agreement with the test results.

Fig. 3 : (a) Load-displacement curve, (b) Delamination failure index of specimen no.1 with EA9309.3NA adhesive.

Fig. 4 : (a) Load-displacement curve, (b) Delamination failure index of co-cured specimen no.5 without adhesive.

Fig. 4 is the failure prediction result of the co-cured specimen without adhesive. The failure load of this specimen is larger than the secondary bonded specimen, but non-linearity does not appear at the load-displacement curve, because this specimen does not have the plastic behavior of adhesive. The load-displacement curve and the delamination failure load predicted show good agreements with the test results.

Fig. 5 shows the failure prediction results of the co-cured specimen with FM73 adhesive. The prediction results show that the bondline failure occurs at 22.8kN and the delamination failure occurs at 12.9kN, showing a quiet large difference between them. This specimen, that is, has very high bondline failure load but is very weak to the delamination failure. Therefore, the failure load of this specimen is 12.9kN, and it is predicted that the previous co-cured specimen without adhesive as well as the secondary bonded specimen have larger failure load than this specimen. This results are also in very good agreement with the test result.

Fig. 5 : (a) Load-displacement curve, (b) Delamination failure index of co-cured specimen no.4 with FM73 adhesive

Fig. 6 : (a) Load-displacement curve, (b) Delamination failure index of co-cured specimen no.4 with FM73 adhesive

Fig. 6 shows the prediction results of the secondary bonded specimen with EA9309NA and with fillets. This results show that the critical failure mode is the bondline failure. The failure mode and strength are in good agreements with the test results. Effect of the fillets can be observed when the results of Fig. 6 are compared with those of Fig. 3. The bondline failure load of the secondary bonded joint is fairly increased with fillet. Also, fillets have the effect of preventing and delaying of the delamination failure. Therefore, the present prediction method well evaluates how fillets affect failure characteristics of the single lap bonded joint. The failure prediction results of all the specimens are summarized and compared with test results in table 3. The failure mode and strength of the composite single lap joints are affected by the bonding methods, the adhesive strength, and fillets. It can be seen that the present method precisely predict the critical failure mode and failure strength of all the specimens considering various bonding parameters.

Table 3 : Summary of failure prediction results.

No	Specimen		Test result		Failure prediction		Error
	Adhesive	Fillet	Failure load (kN)	Failure mode	Failure load (kN)	Failure mode	
1	EA9309.3NA	None	14.0	Bondline	13.8	Same as test	-1.4%
2	EA9309NA	None	14.7	Bondline	14.7	"	0.0%
3	EA9309NA	fillet	17.7	Bondline	17.4	"	-1.6%
4	FM73	None	12.0	Delamination	12.4	"	3.0%
5	None	None	17.3	Delamination	16.8	"	-2.9%

4.3 Failure Characteristics of Composite Single Lap Bonded Joints

Fig. 7 shows the failure prediction results with respect to variations of the effective ultimate stress of the adhesive. Effects of the bonding method and the plastic behaviour of the adhesive can be also evaluated from the results of Fig. 7. First, it can be seen that the co-cured joints without adhesive have the larger failure strength than the adhesively bonded joints because they not only exclude the bondline failure but also have the largest failure load of delamination as shown in Fig. 7(b). Fig. 7(b) shows that the plastic behaviour of adhesive reduces the delamination failure load of the adhesively bonded joint compared to elastic behaviour of adhesive. Therefore, the co-curing method without adhesive is the best method in the composite single lap joints irrespective of performance of adhesive.

Fig. 7 : (a) Load-displacement curve, (b) Delamination failure index with respect to variation of adhesive effective ultimate stress.

For certain case when the adhesive is used in the single lap bonded joints, the failure mode and strength can be changed by variation of the adhesive strength. The failure mode and strength of the joint with respect to the adhesive effective strength are shown schematically in Fig. 8. The graph in Fig. 8 can be easily obtained from the results of Fig. 7.

Fig. 8 shows that the joint with weak adhesive fails in the bondline failure and the failure strengths of these joints are proportionate with the adhesive effective strength. When the adhesive strength is increased to the certain value and the delamination and bondline failure occur simultaneously, the joint has the best strength at this point. If the adhesive strength is increased over this optimal value, this case corresponds to the joint with strong adhesive, the joint strength decrease and hold a uniform lower value. This characteristic can explain why the strength of the composite single lap bonded joint is not always proportionate with the adhesive strength.

Fig. 8 : Failure mode and strength of composite bonded joints w.r.t. adhesive strength.

5. CONCLUSION

A methodology is presented for the failure prediction of composite single-lap bonded joints considering both of composite adherend failure and bondline failure. An elastic-perfectly plastic model of adhesive and a delamination failure criterion were used in the methodology. The failure predictions have been performed using finite element method and the proposed methodology. The failure prediction results such as failure mode and strength have very good agreements with the test results of the joint specimens with various bonding methods and parameters. The influence of variations in the effective strength (that is, adhesion performance) and plastic behavior of the adhesive on the failure characteristics of the composite bonded joints were investigated numerically. The numerical results showed that optimal joint strength is archived when adhesive and delamination failures occur at the same time.

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